

PROGRESS REPORT FLAGSHIP PROJECT

SPOKE1

SPace Activities and CompEtences for industrY bOost in bUsiness

DELIVERABLE D3.0.2

NODES - Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

PROGRESS REPORT FLAGSHIP PROJECT

SPace Activities and CompEtences for industrY bOost in bUsiness

Space4You

SPOKE N 1 Deliverable 3.0.2

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.

Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

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1 EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

1.1 Objectives

The proposed laboratory, Space4You, shall tackle the challenges stemming out from the great attention devoted by the industry to Space and the consequential opportunities. The initial set-up of the lab addressed several different aspects related to the consolidation of the research work of the different teams and the coordination in a unified framework able to provide solutions for increasing the capabilities and outcomes of small satellites missions.

In particular the work is developed in the areas of:

- Design of space architectures for supporting innovative applications and services
- Development of technologies, materials, equipment, and processes for preparation and sustainable implementation of new applications
- Solutions for increasing autonomy of space habitats

As part of the Research Booster methodology of NODES, Space4You will carry out applied research activities with and for companies, to ensure an effective interaction between leading universities and research centers, scientific and industrial associations, important players from the industry, society, and policy makers. It will nurture ideas, inventions, and innovations generated in universities and transfer them to the industrial and social networks, fostering the relations, synergies, and cross-fertilization between different sectors.

During these first 7 months of the project. the initial work was devoted to organize and set-up in a unified framework different contribution by the research partners, which, by themselves, are already performing high-level investigations in the field of applied research for Space.

The Research Module 0 coordinated the activities among the different partners, reviewing the activities already in place and discussing how they can be steered towards the creation of the distributed lab Space4You. The RM1, RM2, RM3 and RM4 all started at RM4 encompass initial research activities performed by the different partners in the fields of Design, Development, Operation and Exploitation of space systems, respectively. The details of the activities performed are summarized in Section 1.2 of the document.

1.2 Explanation of the work carried out per RM in the reporting period

1.2.1 Research Module 0

Research Module n.0	Start month: M1	End month: M36
Title: SETUP AND IMPLEMENTATION OF SPACE4YOU LAB		
Location in Mezzogiorno: N		
RM Leader	PoliTo	
Partners involved	PoliTo	UniTo Links
Type of action:	Industrial Research	
Effort in person/months:	20.24	0.54 3.16
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):		
Initial activities to coordinate the research teams and to set up the distributed laboratory		
Summary of the performed activities		
<i>Task 0.1 Lab setup and management</i>		
PoliTO/ DET and DIMEAS		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparation of the Flagship project description • Preparation of the dissemination material presented to the companies during the dissemination events, Set-up of a collaborative tool for documents management and meeting organization through a dedicated Microsoft Teams group involving all the participants to the project • Organization of monthly internal meetings • Cooperation with other Spokes of NODES for the coordination of the professional education activities • Dissemination and engagement activities towards the aerospace companies of the NODES ecosystem 		
All partners/Research teams		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation to internal meetings to present and coordinate the different research activities • Contribution to the Flagship Project statement of work • Initial drafting of deliverable D1 (Space4You description) and D4 (website) • Administrative procurement procedures for the improvement of new instrumentation for research labs 		
<i>Task 0.2 Ecosystem development</i>		
<p>PoliTO/DIGEP The task aims at improving the understanding of the key factors that affect the process of new business creation and growth in the field of aerospace. Such factors pertain both new business opportunities engendered by technological change and the localized interaction dynamics among different players of the innovation ecosystem. More specifically, we are conducting econometric analyses that will investigate the role of innovation ecosystems in spurring entrepreneurial activities in the space sector and the impact of innovation in space technologies on other industrial sectors. In order to achieve this goals, the research activities have started with the creation of 3 databases on new ventures in Europe, on patent applications in space technologies and on Venture Capital investors. During the first 7 months of the project the research have involved the following activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Datasets:</u> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. DB1: We are generating a new database related to 400 EU-based new startups, founded in the last 8 years and operating in the space sector. Data were collected from the Dealroom database. Firm-level data have been then integrated with individual data on the characteristics of the founders using information from LinkedIn. Each statup has been classified according to a large set of variables that include technological and industrial specialization, economic performance, fundraising capabilities, links with academic and industrial partners, geographical location, the educational and work background of the founders. 		

2. DB2: We are finalizing the collection of patent data related to the space sector. Data have been collected through the database Clarivate. The final database is expected to include about 25 thousands patents filed to the European Patent Office over the last 10 years. In order to identify the relevant set patents, we have used multiple approaches that rely on the use of IPC codes and the names of companies specialized in space technologies. For each patent included in the sample we have retrieved the complete legal and bibliometric data. In particular, we have collected forward citations and identified the characteristics of the citing patents and the related patent applicant.
3. DB3: We are collecting data on the Venture Capital funds in Europe that have carried out equity investments in aerospace startups. We have collected information, mainly using CrunchBase as a data sources, on the financial endowments of the funds and on the specific deals. Each VC fund has been classified as Space-specialised or Non-Space specialized. We have also retrieved data on each target firm. The data allow us to analyses investment rounds in which more than one VC fund has invested (VC Syndication).

We envisage the completion of the data collection of the future 6 months. The final datasets will be treated according to the Data Management Plan of the NODES project and will be account as research results in the next reporting period.

- Design of statistical analysis:

In parallel to the collection of data on startups, VC funds and patents, during the first months of the project we have been working on the design of the econometric models to address a set of specific research questions. In particular, we have worked on the operationalization of this initial set of issues:

1. Analyzing the impact of the location of a space startup in a more/less developed innovation ecosystem on its subsequent financial performance.
2. Assessing the correlation between the founding teams characterizes (previous experience in the sector, diversity of education background, diversity in age) and the success of the startups, comparing companies operating in the upstream or downstream sector.
3. Measuring the rate of transmission of innovative knowledge from space to non-space applications (through patent citations) and disentangling such rate across different technological domains and geographical regions (US vs. Europe).
4. Analyzing the investment strategies of VC funds (portfolio composition, propensity to syndication, specialization in specific tech segments) operating in Europe in the growing sector of the New Space Economy.

Task 0.3 Assessment and sustainability

Polito/DIGEP This task aims at assessing the project results and at putting them in a wider perspective for future exploitation, also planning future activities based on the lab availability and possible growth.

During the first months of the project such objectives have been pursued by aligning the topics of the applied research with those of the academic POCs in order to foster the opportunities for research to work on actual applications. Moreover, the potential services based on the know-how of the lab have been discussed. The long termed sustainability plan will be discussed in the next semester, when feedbacks from industry will be received.

Output and results:

- Initial draft of D1 and D4

Deviations (if applicable):

The large number of partners involved belonging to different institutions and different departments within the organisations themselves, required a relevant effort in establishing the links for the coordination of the future activities. For this reason, the preparation of the deliverable D1 is experiencing some delay.

The preparation of D4 (FP website) had to be coordinated with the other spokes and is ongoing but not yet finalized, even if the first version of the website page is expected to be issued in the next few weeks.

Both the delays are not impacting the activities of the other RMs which started as planned.

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

None

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

- Organisation of internal meeting to foster the collaboration among the participants
- Discussion of the long-term sustainability plan of the Lab
- Finalisation of D1 and D4

1.2.2 Research Module 1

Research Module n.1	Start month: M4	End month: M36
Title: DESIGN		
Location in Mezzogiorno: N		
RM Leader	PoliTo	
Partners involved	PoliTo	UniTo
Type of action:	Industrial Research	
Effort in person/months:	1.54	1.80

Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):
Research studies to support the DESIGN phase of space systems

Summary of the performed activities

Task 1.1 Concurrent & virtual design

PoliTO/DIMEAS: The requirements for the improvement of the existing Concurrent Engineering System (CES) have been defined according to the result of the analysis of the project needs and objectives. A preliminary study aimed at assessing the technical and programmatic feasibility of the proposed improvements has been carried out. A set of criteria for the selection of most suitable/interesting improvements has been defined, together with a preliminary set of possible use cases to be used for the validation of the improved CES.

Task 1.2 Simulation models

PoliTO/DISMA: A numerical tool for domain decomposition of coupled 3D-2D problems has been investigated, based on the introduction of interface variables for de-coupling the problems on domains with different geometrical size. A prototype demonstration code has been developed, capable of handling 3D-2D coupled problems with relatively simple geometries. The generalization to arbitrarily complex problems will be addressed next.

PoliTO/DIMEAS: At system level some specific simulation modelling techniques for thermal systems have been developed. In particular commercial tools for thermal analysis have been adapted to consider the effects of the lunar soil thermal radiation on the futuristic infrastructures on the Moon surface (power generation systems, habitats, rovers and mechatronics, etc.) inspired to the NASA ARTEMIS scenario. Referring to some applications (thermal radiators of power generation systems, windows for pressurized modules, and on-board components for exploration rovers) special engineering thermal models have been developed with the definition of useful temperature measurement points to implement suitable thermal control laws and to detect thermal functions degradation.

LINKS/CPE: The main approaches to implement a digital twin based on data gathered through a satellite constellation has been explored. In particular, upon high resolution images from a satellite constellation of a specific area on Earth, a digital twin model can be built. Building such a model requires a lot of computational resources, thus the adoption of a HPC approach can help to reduce the time required for the analysis. However, the first step has been state-of-the-art research of the possible approaches and algorithms to find the better approach to achieve the desired digital twin model. A preliminary implementation of the selected approach has been performed to fine tune the final model. A fully detailed model is expected at the end of the analysis, to support the decision making process on how to define future strategies, especially in case of a digital twin model derived from Earth observation images from satellite.

UNITO/DIP Matematica: The study of the aggregation and movement of celestial bodies has been started from a computational point of view. As part of a collaboration between researchers specialized in the field of theoretical analysis, numerical analysis and machine learning, the setup of a deep neural network able to explore

the space of the solutions of the trajectories subject to symmetries and positional constraints, has been performed.

Task 1.3 ICT technologies

Polito/DET: Different approaches for simulating satellite networks are considered, in order to evaluate different architectures to support ICT services across a satellite infrastructure. The source and destination of the communications can be either the satellites or ground/lunar stations. The initial requirements for the simulator have been defined. Depending on the scalability requirements of the simulator, different architectures are defined.

LINKS/CPE: a server rack has been designed and implemented, based on the OpenStack cloud approach. This rack is used as a test node for developing cloud computing algorithms for simulations and digital twin scenarios. Different configuration and interconnections among the various hardware and software modules in order to find the best setup of the system. The server stack will be able to run simulations in order to help small companies to better tune the missions, as well as it will support the elaboration of data coming from the satellites to create a digital twin of a specific area on the ground.

Task 1.4 Generic technologies

Polito/DIMEAS: The requirements for novel visual navigation algorithms for proximity operations of small distributed systems in safety-critical context have been defined taking into account a case of interest. The selected use case refers to a nanosatellite performing a rendezvous and docking mission with a mothercraft in Low Earth Orbit.

Polito/DIMEAS: Leveraging on the background experience of the Photonext interdepartmental center the optic measurement of the temperature of space subsystems has been thorough, in particular, the FBG sensing technology. Some FBG sensors packaging techniques has been specifically designed for the temperature measurement of radiators, windows and tanks of lunar infrastructures.

Polito/DISEG: The development of future spaceports as civil infrastructures is a crucial aspect of advancing space activities. The research team in DISEG is actively collaborating on the design and development of the only one Italian spaceport in Grottaglie, in accordance with the plans set forth by the Italian National Airports Authority. The team's efforts focus on various activities such as site selection, infrastructure design, regulatory compliance, safety protocols, and logistical considerations. This collaboration involves working closely with aerospace companies, government agencies, and international partners to ensure the spaceport's compatibility with future space missions. The ultimate objective is to create a comprehensive blueprint that addresses the technical, operational, and regulatory requirements for the successful establishment of the spaceport. The research conducted by the team will contribute valuable insights to the overall development of spaceports as vital facilities supporting space exploration endeavors.

UniTO/Chemistry: The research of the Unit focuses on Materials technologies enabling space exploration. Leveraging on previous projects funded by Regione Piemonte (STEPS, SMAT, STEPS2), ASI and ESA, the team has undertaken a refocusing of the research activities, also in collaboration with the major industrial stakeholders. The experimental capacity to produce relevant data and conceptual innovation has been reviewed. As a result of this process, the available expertises have been prioritized according to their potential for development, identifying the fields in which the team/project can yield higher impact. High impact fields are identified as: a) lightweight PV technologies; b) the chemistry of CO₂, water and fuels in Life Support Systems, c) Material chemistry for In Situ Resource Utilization, d) Heat and Radiation shields.

Output and results:

Final selection and set up of the activities to be developed in the project

Identification of detailed objectives and requirements for next period activities
Preliminary studies and iterations on some research topics

Deviations (if applicable):

No deviations from planning

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

None

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

PoliTO/DIMEAS: Consolidation of the requirements to be implemented the new release of the Concurrent Engineering System (CES). Trade-off study for the selection of one reference use case to be used for the validation of the improved CES. Identification of the tools to be integrated in the software suite of the CES.

PoliTO/DISEG: Definition of the blueprint that addresses the technical, operational, and regulatory requirements for the successful establishment of the spaceport.

PoliTO/DET: Definition of the architecture of the communication simulator.

1.2.3 Research Module 2

Research Module n.2	Start month: M4			End month: M36			
Title: DEVELOPMENT							
Location in Mezzogiorno: N							
RM Leader	PoliTo						
Partners involved	PoliTo	UniTo	Links				
Type of action:	<i>Industrial Research</i>						
Effort in person/months:	10.83	0.46	0				
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):							
Research studies to support the DEVELOPMENT phase of space systems.							
Summary of the performed activities							
<i>Task 2.1 Manufacturing processes</i>							
<p>PoliTO/DIMEAS: The DIMEAS research unit has acquired experience on the plasma treatment of fibres in composite materials and adherends in adhesive joints thanks to internal research activities and to collaborations with automotive industries (e.g., POR-FESR Project, Green Factory for Composites). The research unit successfully worked on the application of plasma treatments on composite laminates and adhesive joints. The activity proved that the mechanical properties of composite materials and adhesive joints can significantly increase by using plasma treatments. In the reference period), the DIMEAS unit reviewed the existing competences and facilities of the distributed lab and defined the activities that will be carried out in the next months.</p> <p>PoliTO/DISAT: Ceramic materials (bulk and composites) can withstand harsh environments and can also provide specific mechanical properties, such as high elastic modulus and strength, coupled with low density. These properties make them interesting for challenging applications, where harsh conditions (e.g. high/very low temperatures, aggressive chemicals, etc.) have to be taken into consideration, for example, in the aerospace fields. It is usually necessary to join certain parts to manufacture the desired product.</p> <p>Among the possible solutions that can be proposed to improve the performances of ceramic joints, one consists in creating an interlocking between the composites and the joining material. DISAT unit focussed its research activity on this topic, using different modification techniques and testing several modified surfaces. One promising approach relies on the use of a laser to obtain a texturized surface, that overcomes the typical issues concerning surface mechanical machining, such as tool wear and crack formation. On the contrary, chemical etching of ceramic material (i.e SiC, the most common ceramic for satellites) is a challenging process because of its chemical inertness. Moreover, it is a costly and less environmentally friendly approach. Other modification surfaces processes involve the plasma-based etching techniques, which are known to be effective for the modification of ceramic surfaces. These techniques provide accurate control of the process but impose strict limitations on the maximum size and number of the components that can be treated. Furthermore, the equipment is usually complex and a high-level of maintenance is required. On the contrary, atmospheric-pressure plasmas (APPs) are of interest when large samples need to be treated, since they provide several advantages over low-pressure plasmas. POLITO has recently demonstrated that the use of corona plasma can modify the surface of SiC ceramic, thus resulting in an increase of the adhesion at the SiC/adhesive interface in adhesively bonded SiC.</p> <p>In the reference period, the DISAT unit studied the feasibility of the texturing of ceramic surfaces by Atmospheric-pressure plasmas (APPs). The mechanical anchoring created by texturing is expected to enhance the mechanical strength of bonded samples and lead to cohesive failure. The surface modification process, coupled with suitable joining material, can be a significant added value in the proposed activity. After the definition of the processes parameters to produce a textured composite surface, the specimen surfaces will be</p>							

characterized in terms of the topography of the surface and bending tests to value the effect of the modification process among treated and non-treated samples.

Polito/DISAT: In aerospace applications, ceramics are primarily found in engine and exhaust systems, thermal protection shields, and structures for ultra high-speed flying objects. Ceramics that can withstand temperatures as high as 1,600 °C are used to manufacture lightweight turbine components that require less cooling air, such as vanes, blades, nozzles, and combustion liners, and parts for the exhaust system that enhance acoustic attenuation and have a long life thanks to their abrasion and corrosion resistance. Furthermore, ceramics additive manufacturing dramatically enlarged the number of possibilities and potential applications of ceramic components in the aerospace industry thanks to an easier manufacturing method of complex-shaped and customizable parts. Therefore, the DISAT research unit devoted the reference period (M4-M7) to the definition of the different activities to be carried out in the next coming months exploiting the possessed strong background both in the field of advanced ceramics and ceramics 3D printing. In particular, different ceramic oxides (alumina, zirconia, alumina-zirconia composites, aluminosilicates etc.) will be developed and used in the Digital Light Processing (DLP) 3D printing technique. These materials can be optimized and engineered through well-established and experimental synthesis and processing methods as well as by adding reinforcing agents, such as platelets, to improve thermal shock and fracture toughness properties.

Polito/DISEG: The colonization of celestial bodies, including the Moon and other planets, presents a significant challenge in establishing sustainable human habitats capable of supporting life for extended periods. Minimizing reliance on Earth-derived materials due to transportation costs is a key aspect. An alternative approach involves utilizing local resources, such as regolith and moon water, while leveraging 3D printing technology to construct in-situ structures like domes. This rewrite focuses on the preliminary design and optimization of 3D printed domes, considering structural performance under real loads and the unique conditions of reduced gravity. Additionally, the incorporation of reusable pneumatic formwork for complex shape construction through 3D printing is explored.

Defining an Optimal Shape for Structural Performance: A crucial element of this research involves defining an optimal shape for domes to ensure optimal structural performance. The DISEG research unit has dedicated the reference period to define the different activities for the upcoming months, considering preliminary design criteria for such structures. Factors such as the requirement of negative pressure (equivalent to Earth's air pressure) and the reduced self-weight due to lower gravity are considered in the analysis of real loads acting on the structures. This analysis enables the determination of the most efficient shape that provides structural stability and integrity in the extraterrestrial environment. Preliminary analytical structural models are being evaluated to describe more interesting structural and technological solutions.

Utilization of Local Materials: The utilization of local materials, such as regolith and moon water, is a vital aspect of this research. By harnessing the capabilities of 3D printing technology, regolith can be processed and used as a building material for constructing the domes. Moon water, which can be extracted and utilized for various purposes, including binding the regolith, further enhances the feasibility of constructing human habitats on celestial bodies. The research emphasizes the use of "lunar concrete" and its viscoelastic-to-hardened transition, and specific mechanical simulations are being conducted to evaluate the transient construction phases in conjunction with the use of local materials.

Construction Stage: Reusable Pneumatic Formwork: To enable the construction of complex shapes through 3D printing, the DISEG research unit is exploring the use of reusable pneumatic formwork. This innovative approach involves creating temporary molds or structures that provide support during printing, facilitating the realization of intricate and customized dome designs. The formwork can be pressurized to achieve the desired shape and then quickly removed or repositioned for subsequent printing stages. The research team is conducting specific mechanical simulations to evaluate the construction phases and the behavior of the "lunar concrete" during the viscoelastic-to-hardened transition. The utilization of reusable pneumatic formwork is of specific interest in this research developed by the DISEG research units it could enhance the efficiency and flexibility of the construction process, allowing for the creation of complex geometries that meet the particular requirements of long-term human habitats. Some more specific analyses dealing with 3d printing technology

limitation, optimal structural shape (minimizing masses or earth delivery materials) and use of pneumatic formworks will be deeply analyzed to propose preliminary design solutions.

Task 2.2 smart AIV/T

Polito/DIMEAS: The definition of strategies for supporting the verification and testing of small space systems started. The research is aimed at finding processes/tools for reducing the duration and the cost of the verification/testing campaign, while increasing the effectiveness of the verification/testing activities with the final goal of increasing mission success.

Task 2.3 ICT Technologies

Polito/DAUIN: Research activities in ICT technologies are dedicated to the design of deep neural networks (DNNs) that meet high standards in terms of accuracy, efficiency and robustness, tackling this issue from a hardware and software perspective. Recruitment of research staff (1 PhD student) was successfully concluded in February. During the first period (M4-M7), the current state of the art on fault-tolerant DNNs, from the standpoints of DNN design and learning algorithms, was thoroughly assessed. The DAUIN team decided to focus on computer vision applications first, including satellite imagery processing. Since the current literature is often limited to toy datasets and specific architectures, a thorough set of experiments was conducted to assess the interplay between DNN architecture (Convolutional Neural Network, Residual networks, EfficientNet, MobileNet, Transformers), the dataset and the training method, including the effect of quantization, on the robustness to simple faults (e.g. bit flip). In this initial phase, software-induced faults were considered to broaden the range of tested configurations. The experimental results will lay the basis for the next steps devoted to developing a more realistic fault model by moving to a hardware-in-the-loop setting.

Polito/DET: During this first phase of the project the development of a physical layer signal simulator started. These software elements will be integrated in the software-defined radio reconfigurable test-bench for testing communication architectures for small satellites to be used on Earth orbits as well as communication nodes in space missions (e.g. to the Moon village). Signals used for ranging channels are included as well, in order to support the testing of positioning and navigation techniques.

The software modules are designed with a flexible approach and currently include the generation of signals foreseen by the CCSDS recommendations, but also more modern proposals from the scientific literature.

As for the navigation part, a revision of the already available Software-defined implementation of GNSS receivers was undertaken in order to simplify interfaces among the different stages, and prepare it to be integrated in the test-bench.

Polito/DET: A store-carry-forward paradigm is considered for the satellite networks and for providing connectivity to ground/lunar stations. According to it, satellite acts as “data mules” when no end-to-end communication is allowed between the source and destination nodes which can be either satellites or ground station. We are devising the routing and data forwarding policies to maximize the performance (i.e., maximum throughput and minimum latency) given the memory budget available at the satellites. In case of small satellites, stringent memory requirements are considered.

Task 2.4 Generic technologies

Polito/DIMEAS: Some initial attempts to implement a technology demonstrator of a space graded multipurpose measurement chain using FBG optical sensors, useful for the thermal management/control of power units and for the monitoring of the lunar habitats, have been developed, with specific reference to MLI and windows temperature monitoring, and tested in laboratory.

UniTO/DipFisica: The first phase of the project has been dedicated to the procurement of instrumentation for the enhancement of the X-ray Calibration Facility (XCF). The facility is hosted in the Physics Department (UniTO) and has been designed for the characterization of innovative X-ray sensors. In particular, the acquired auto dry cabinet will enable the storage of sensors and components at controlled temperature and humidity.

The acquired laminar flow hood will ensure a protection from external and cross contamination during the manufacturing and assembling of detectors.

Output and results:

PoliTO/DIMEAS: Assessment of the steps to be covered for the efficient and effective application of plasma treatments to fibres in structural composites.

PoliTO/DISAT: Feasibility of surface engineering of ceramic based materials by atmospheric plasma pressure.

PoliTO/DISAT: Investigation of the different applications of advanced ceramics used in the aerospace sector, with particular attention to those shaped via vat-photopolymerization techniques. A paragraph of a review submitted to the journal *Frontiers in Materials* is related to this topic.

All:

Final selection and set up of the activities to be developed in the project

Identification of detailed objectives and requirements for next period activities

Preliminary studies and iterations on some research topics

Deviations (if applicable):

No deviations from planning

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

None

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

PoliTO/DIMEAS: Execution of preliminary steps for the application of plasma treatments to fibres in structural composites. In particular, definition of the methodology for the optimized application of the plasma treatments and subsequent mechanical characterization to prove the effectiveness of the plasma treatment by using standard (e.g., double cantilever beam tests and end notched flexural tests) and non-standard (nano-indentations) testing procedures.

PoliTO/DIMEAS: Definition of requirements for the tools to be integrated into the verification and testing flow, with focus on applications for supporting the development of visual navigation algorithms.

PoliTO/DISAT: Preliminary experimental trials on surface engineering of ceramic based materials by atmospheric plasma pressure and definition of the methodology for the optimized application of the plasma treatments. Moreover, a mutual activity with DIMEAS unit will be carried on, focussing on the investigation of surface modification processes on polymeric-based composites reinforced by C fibers. DISAT unit will supply the microstructural characterization of the modified surfaces by means of microscopic analysis by OM and SEM coupled with EDS, zeta potential and micro-CT, accordingly to what detailed in the previous paragraph.

PoliTO/DISAT: Future research will investigate not only technological aspects of the manufacturing process but also the relationships between processing, microstructure and properties of ceramics sintered at high temperatures. To this extent, controlling the nano/microstructure as well as the composition, engineered ceramic components will be developed. Optimization of ceramics formulations to be used as thermal barrier coatings; definition and engineering of alumina-zirconia textured ceramics with improved fracture toughness and thermal shock resistance.

PoliTO/DET: Development of the physical layer communication simulator, study of routing and data forwarding policies

1.2.4 Research Module 3

Research Module n.3	Start month: M4			End month: M36			
Title: OPERATIONS							
Location in Mezzogiorno: N							
RM Leader	PoliTo						
Partners involved	PoliTo	UniTo	Links				
Type of action:	Industrial Research						
Effort in person/months:	0.78	0	0				
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):							
Research studies to support the OPERATIONS phase of space systems							
Summary of the performed activities							
<i>Task 3.3 Data management</i>							
<p>PoliTO/DISMA: The activity on the task focused on the analysis of the currently available techniques for efficient data management.</p> <p>PoliTO/DAUIN: Data management innovation is nowadays driven by the application of AI/ML/DL solutions for several applications that require, fast and reliable analysis of large amount of data, statistical characterization, and automated decision support. In this context, it is envisioned that data processing will be performed both on board and/or on ground. Activities on this task focused primarily on the robustness of on-board processing, in connection with activities on Task 2.3. Specifically, experiments were conducted on networks trained on earth observation imagery to investigate connections between the characteristics of the input images and training datasets with the fault-tolerance of the trained deep neural networks.</p>							
Output and results:							
Final selection and set up of the activities to be developed in the project							
Identification of detailed objectives and requirements for next period activities							
Preliminary studies and iterations on some research topics							
Deviations (if applicable):							
No deviations from planning							
Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:							
None							
Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:							
Start activities on Tasks 3.1 and 3.2							

1.2.5 Research Module 4

Research Module n.4	Start month: M4			End month: M36			
Title: EXPLOITATION							
Location in Mezzogiorno: N							
RM Leader	PoliTo						
Partners involved	PoliTo	UniTo	Links				
Type of action:	Industrial Research						
Effort in person/months:	5.65	0.46	0				
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):							
Research studies to support the EXPLOITATION phase of space systems							
Summary of the performed activities							
<i>Task 4.1. Modern satellite communication services</i>							
<p>PoliTO/DET: We have started to consider different approaches to evaluate the performance in terms of delays and throughput for a network of cooperative satellites. We have identified the following approaches. (i) Formal methods are developed based on time-space graphs, designed specifically for Delay Tolerant Networks (DTN). (ii) Specific libraries, tailored for satellite networks, are developed for generic network simulators (e.g., OMNet++). (iii) Ad-hoc simulators are developed for the considered network scenario. The preliminary state-of-the-art analysis has been started.</p>							
<i>Task 4.2 Earth Observation</i>							
<p>PoliTO/DIMEAS: During the considered period, activities have been focused on collecting and conveniently store relevant Earth Observation data, including the following metocean data: significant wave height, peak wave period, wave direction, wind speed at 10m height, and mean wind direction. In addition, in-situ measurements are included in the same database, to enable meaningful comparison and quantitative evaluation of the results. A first step of refinement and calibration of the data is performed through Copernicus Marine Services, where filtering and co-location analysis improves the accuracy and reliability of the raw data, also in comparison with available in-situ data.</p>							
<p>LINKS/ADS: In the period under analysis Links contributed to modernizing and repurposing the in-house laboratory in a larger scope of collaboration with partners. The laboratory is being reimagined also for the new frontier of Machine Learning/AI, applied to field of interest such as space technologies. Existing infrastructure optimized for high computational loads to support AI development will also be reachable from the laboratory. Links is also focused on supporting test facilities that will research AI application domains. One of these being earth observation. Earth observation can be aided by machine learning</p>							
<p>PoliTO/DIST: In the considered period a consistent activity related to data acquisition related to the production of 3D model ha been carried out; in particular aerial multispectral acquisitions complemented by high density lidar point cloud collection have been executed. With this aim, different products related to the urban area of Torino, have been deployed: high resolution orthoprojection, photogrammetric and lidar classified point clouds and photorealistic 3D meshes. In the meantime, a tasking activity related to VHR resolution multistereo and multispectral acquisitions has been planned; as soon as the raw data will be delivered, a research activity related to automatic image orientation will be possibly defined, enabling DSM production and accuracy assessment procedure implementation with the aim to precisely define use cases and scale representation.</p>							

Task 4.3 Navigation and Geo-Positioning services

PoliTO/DET: During this period the activity addressed the study of new signals suitable to the use in modern GNSS system, focusin on LEO-PNT architecture and the use not only of the classical L-Band, but also S-Band and Ka/Ku bands allowing the use of wideband signals. A study to identify the best candidates have been performed takinginto account different metric (Gabor Bandwidth, robustness to multipath and interference, complexity). Specific studies addressed the Multilevel Coded Spreading Symbols modulations.

Regarding the set-up of the lab facilities, hardware equipment for the installation of a GNSS monitoring station has been purchased. The installation will take place in a shared lab between PoliTO and LINKS.

LINKS/ADS: Throughout the period Links/ADS addressed the possibility of the application of AI to the domain of signal analisys specifically in the case of GNSS. It is seen in the literature how AI/ML algorithms can be used to address the problem of GNSS interference. Links/ADS has also envisioned its laboratory infrastructures in a collaborative mindset, willing to support development projects in the realm of AI/ML applied to navigation, and signal analysis.

Task 4.4. Space Exploration

PoliTO/DET: The preliminary activities have been devoted to the review of the latest updates of the LUNANET documentation of NASA and the lates advancements of the Moonlight initiative of the European Space Agency, defining the architectures foreseen for the Lunar communication and navigation systems, in order to prepare the simulation/emulation environment to be implemented in the Space4You lab.

UniTO/DipFisica: The first tests on the set up of the X-ray Calibration Facility (XCF), hosted in the Physics Department (UniTO) for the characterization of innovative X-ray sensors, have started. The radiation source is an X-ray tube with a multi-anode to select the desired energy and two beam lines: one is unpolarized, the other one is polarized via Bragg diffraction on a polarizing crystal. Thanks to a handling system, the detector to be tested can measure both the unpolarized and polarized beam. By comparing these two signals X-ray sensors can be calibrated and characterized.

We are currently testing a Gas Pixel Detector, similar to those currently flying on the Imaging X-ray Polarimetry Explorer (IXPE). Preliminary results are compatible with the expected performances. We will undertake a complete characterization study of this detector, in order to improve the design for the next generation of experiments designed to allow for a significantly larger data throughput (e.g. eXTP).

Output and results:

Final selection and set up of the activities to be developed in the project
Identification of detailed objectives and requirements for next period activities
Preliminary studies and iterations on some research topics

Deviations (if applicable):

No deviations from plan

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling reserach activities:

Hardware equipment for the implementation of the GNSS station in the lab

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

PoliTO/DET and **LINKS/ADS** will finalize the installation of the GNSS station in the shared lab

PoliTO/DAUIN: start activities on application of AI to earth observation applications

Key Indicators for Research activities and Flagship Projects:

Action	Key Indicator	SPOKE' overall target	Flagship progress
Outcome	Number of Pilot Line / Demonstrators / Prototypes	5 demonstrators, 1 prototype	-
	Number of publications	21 journal papers / 30 publications in international conferences	-
	Number of registered IPR (patents, utility models, trademarks, industrial designs)	1 patent	
Output	Number of professor and researcher involved	25	33
	Personnel effort dedicated to Research and Innovation and Flagship Project (person/month in three years)	341 PM	47.41PM

1. IMPACT

This first phase of the project has been mainly devoted to:

- the implementation of the management structure of the FP and the coordination of the different actors involved
- the final identification and set up of the research activities

For this reasons, the number of outcomes and products is still limited.

No publication is available yet, however a Journal publication and three conference contributions have been submitted and are currently under review.

No IPR has been produced yet. Three datasets are currently being compiled and will be finalized by the next reporting period.

2. INDUSTRY PARTICIPATION AND INNOVATIONS

In this initial phase of the applied research activities the engagement of industry has been mostly linked to the involvement of the Stakeholders Committee. Moreover, the contents of the Flagship have been presented in different meetings with companies during the events for the launch of cascade calls. Meetings have been also organised by scientific coordinators with companies interested in the topics of the flagship. All the researchers involved in the FP are intensifying their research relationships with companies. To this end, they are establishing relationships with new companies and to identify topics of real interest where researchers' expertise may be of interest.

The stakeholder committee has been established.

3. FOLLOW-UP OF RECOMMENDATIONS AND COMMENTS FROM PREVIOUS REVIEW(S) (IF APPLICABLE)

Not applicabile

4. OPEN SCIENCE PRACTISES AND UPDATE OF THE DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (IF APPLICABLE)

Not applicabile

5. RESULTS BEYOND THE STATE OF THE ART

The activities of this first phase of the project were mostly devoted to the set-up of the lab and the revision of the state of the art, that will allow advanced research activities in the next steps of the project.

2 ANNEXES

2.1 LIST OF DELIVERABLES

Add actual delivery dates (or new due date for late deliverables, together with an explanation for the delay). In the Comments, please indicate if the deliverable was achieved as planned or not.

The labels used mean:

Public — fully open; Sensitive — limited; R – Restricted; C – Confidential; S – Secret.

Name	RM No	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)	Status	Comments
e4You Lab description	RM0	PoliTO	R	PU	M7	M9		Pending	Description of the organization of the lab
e4You Lab User Guide	RM0	PoliTO	R	SEN	M15				Description of the facilities
e4You Executive Summary Report	RM0	PoliTO	R	PU	M15 (draft) M36 (final)				Description of the pilot activity
e4You website	RM0	PoliTO		PU	M7 (draft) M36 (final)	M8		Pending	Website information about the lab experience

Table 1: Deliverables

3

3.1 LIST OF MILESTONES

Milestone No	Milestone Name	RM No	Lead Beneficiary	Means of Verification	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)	Achieved	Comments
MS0	Milestone 0	RM0	PoliTO		31/12/2022		31/01/2023	YES	Preparation of activity
MS1	Milestone 1	RM0	PoliTO	Issue of deliverable D1 Issue of draft version of deliverable	30/04/2023	30/06/2023		NO	Achievement of the milestone is delayed due to the delay in the delivery of

				D4					D1 and D4
MS2	Milestone 2	RM0	PolITO	Issue of draft version of deliverable D2 Setup of 2 (TBC) pilot projects	31/12/2023				
MS3	Milestone 3	RM0	PolITO	Issue of final version of deliverables D2, D3 and D4	30/09/2025				

Table 2: Milestones

3.2 LIST OF CRITICAL RISKS

No risks have been identified so far.

Risk No	Did you apply risk mitigation measures?	Did your risk materialize?	Comments
[risk number]	[YES] [NO]	[YES] [NO]	[insert comment (mandatory if no risk mitigation measures where applied or planned risk mitigation measures were not applied)]

Table 3: Risks

Table 4: Results

3.3 PUBLICATIONS

No publications have been finalized in this first reporting period. Three conference paper and one Journal paper have been submitted for peer-review and possible publication

3.4 DATASETS

No Datasets have been finalized in this first reporting period

3.5 INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS (IPRs)

No IPR have been generated in this first reporting period

3.6 OTHER RESULTS

No other results have been generated in this first reporting period